

A Comparative Analysis of Sweetness Perception in Selected International Gifflars

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Abstract

The objective of this scientific paper was to investigate the perceived sweetness levels in Swedish and Finnish Gifflars, traditional cinnamon rolls made by Pågen and enjoyed in both Sweden and Finland. While these pastries share a similar name and basic ingredients, there has been a longstanding debate among enthusiasts as to which country's version is sweeter. To expand the scope of this study, also German Gifflars by Pågen, as well as Swedish Fika cinnamon rolls, produced by Himmelsö, are being evaluated. For the investigation, a panel of sensory evaluators with diverse backgrounds and preferences was assembled to conduct a blind test. The panelists underwent extensive training in sensory evaluation techniques to ensure accurate and consistent data collection. All Gifflars were sourced from reputable bakeries in their respective countries, maintaining authenticity in flavor and preparation methods.

Introduction

Culinary traditions often transcend borders, and few things exemplify this as vividly as the Swedish and Finnish Gifflars, popularly known as cinnamon rolls. These delectable pastries, adorned with cinnamon and sugar, have charmed the palates of Nordic enthusiasts for generations. However, a captivating debate has persisted within the culinary realm – are Swedish Gifflars indeed sweeter than their Finnish counterparts? The theory that Swedish Gifflars are sweeter than Finnish Gifflars has tantalized taste buds and sparked countless discussions among connoisseurs. Yet, this debate has largely remained anecdotal, with passionate advocates on both sides offering their subjective opinions. It is a question that has not only intrigued the culinary world but also ignited curiosity within the realm of sensory perception and food science.

This paper embarks on a journey to delve deep into this age-old culinary dispute. Our primary objective is to subject this theory to a rigorous scientific investigation, utilizing sensory analysis and instrumental techniques to provide empirical evidence. By undertaking this study, we aim to shed light on the sweetness levels of these beloved pastries and offer a nuanced perspective grounded in sensory science.

Fundamentals

In the context of this study, two major categories are differentiated: Pågen Gifflars, available in Swe-

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den, Finland, and Germany, and the Himmelsö Fika Cinnamon Rolls, exclusively sold in Sweden. Despite our inquiry, the exact compositions of these variations remain unknown, thus necessitating an assumption that all versions share a common underlying approach, often represented as:

$$\text{Kanel} + \text{bullar} = \text{Kanelbullar}. \quad (1)$$

Pågen Gifflars have charmed the palates of Scandinavians and non-Scandinavians alike. These pastries expertly blend the comforting aroma of cinnamon with the sweetness of the dough, becoming an integral part of Nordic culinary traditions. Himmelsö, a renowned brand in Sweden, offers a distinct take on the beloved cinnamon roll, tailored for Swedish "Fika" enthusiasts. "Fika" is a cherished Swedish tradition, more than just a coffee break; it is a cultural institution that signifies taking a moment to relax, socialize, and enjoy a cup of coffee or tea accompanied by pastries. In figure 1, a schematic drawing of a cinnamon bun is provided for a general overview.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of an arbitrary cinnamon bun.

To facilitate a comprehensive comparison of all investigated cinnamon buns, a detailed overview of their nutritional information is provided in table 1.

Table 1: Nutritional declaration of all cinnamon buns per 100 g.

Parameter	Unit	Pågen			Himmelsö
		Finnish	Swedish	German	Swedish
Energy	[kJ/kcal]	1559/373	1559/373	1559/373	1475/351
Fat	[g]	14	14	14	11
of which saturated	[g]	2.8	2.8	2.8	1.4
Carbohydrates	[g]	52	52	52	57
of which sugars	[g]	19	19	19	20
Protein	[g]	7.3	7.3	7.3	5.7
Salt	[g]	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.6

While the nutritional information of all cinnamon buns under investigation may appear strikingly similar or even identical (see table 1), it is essential to recognize that taste and sweetness are intricate qualities, influenced by multifaceted structures that extend beyond mere nutritional composition. According to the packaging, all cinnamon buns are produced in Sweden.

Studies

Two comprehensive studies were conducted to investigate the sensory preferences and distinctions among various cinnamon bun samples.

The first study involved blind taste-testing of Pågen Gifflars sourced from Finland, Sweden, and Germany. The primary objective was to determine which variant was perceived as the sweetest. In the second study, Finnish Pågen Gifflars were pitted against Himmelsö Fika Cinnamon Buns in a blind test. The aim was to discern the preferred choice between these two distinct cinnamon bun offerings.

Data collection was facilitated through the use of a straightforward survey sheet, where participants could indicate their preferences using the options A, B, C, or Equal (for the first study), or A, B, or Equal (for the second study). These letters corresponded to the various disguised samples of cinnamon buns provided for evaluation. Furthermore, the survey is carried out in a way that the participants are unable to see prior votes in order to avoid any bias.

Results

In this section, the results of the studies are presented. Both studies are presented separately. It is noteworthy to mention that both studies were conducted on separate occasions, leading to a variance in the total number of participants between the two investigations.

Comparison of different Pågen Gifflars

As described above, the first study sought to discern perceived sweetness levels across Pågen Gifflars obtained from Finland, Sweden, and Germany. In total, 34 individuals participated in this study. A graphical representation of the results is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Results of the first study.

Notably, the Swedish Gifflars garnered the highest number of votes for being the sweetest, with 17 out of 34 participants expressing this preference. The Finnish Gifflars followed closely, receiving 9 votes. The German Gifflars, on the other hand, were considered the sweetest by 2 participants. Intriguingly, 6 participants found no noticeable distinction in sweetness among the three variants.

These results offer valuable insights into the subjective perceptions of sweetness in Pågen Gifflars sourced from different regions. With 50% of the votes on the Swedish Gifflars, the results substantiate the hypothesis that Swedish Gifflars exhibit a higher perceived level of sweetness compared to their Finnish counterparts. Furthermore, it is intriguing to observe that even the German Gifflars exhibit a comparatively subdued and less playful character when contrasted with their international counterparts.

Pågen Gifflars vs. Himmelsö Buns

In the second study, focusing on the comparative sensory analysis of Finnish Pågen Gifflars and Swedish Himmelsö Fika Cinnamon Buns, a cohort of 18 participants contributed their evaluations. It is important

to stress that the goal is not to evaluate sweetness, but rather to determine which cinnamon bun is generally considered superior in overall taste and quality. The ensuing results are graphically depicted in figure 3.

Figure 3: Results of the second study.

It is noticeable that 17 respondents unequivocally favored the Finnish PÅgen Gifflars, while only a solitary participant expressed a preference for the Swedish Himmelsö Fika Cinnamon Buns. Intriguingly, none of the participants adjudged the tastes of both options to be of equal merit.

The results not only affirm the superiority of PÅgen Gifflars over the Himmelsö Buns in terms of taste and quality, but they also serve as a reflection of the rich culinary tradition and meticulous craftsmanship that PÅgen has upheld throughout the years. The distinctive flavors and textures of PÅgen Gifflars stand as a testament to the brand's dedication to excellence in pastry-making.

Discussion

This study explores preferences and distinctions among cinnamon buns from different regions and brands. However, it is important to acknowledge potential limitations that may have influenced our findings.

One notable consideration is the potential influence of the order in which the samples were presented and tasted. This sequence could have influenced participants' evaluations, potentially impacting their perception of sweetness. To mitigate this effect, randomization techniques should be implemented in future studies. However, it is essential to recognize that individual preferences and palates may have played a role.

Additionally, the observation that several participants opted to halve the buns, rather than consuming them in their entirety, introduces a noteworthy variable. This practice may have inadvertently altered the composition of the sample. Depending on the cut, there could be a variance in the distribution of cinnamon cream, potentially leading to a perceived difference in sweetness. This factor highlights the

importance of standardizing the evaluation process in future studies.

In the first study, it is worth noting that participants were unable to mark only two buns as equally sweet. While this simplification was intentional to streamline the evaluation process, it may have potentially led to nuanced variations in the data. It is imperative for future studies to consider alternative methodologies that may allow for a more granular assessment of sweetness perceptions.

These considerations may also explain why varying levels of sweetness are perceived, despite all PÅgen Gifflars sharing identical nutritional information. Despite these potential limitations, the study successfully sheds light on the nuanced distinctions in taste preferences among the evaluated cinnamon buns. The findings provide valuable insights into the sensory experiences associated with these beloved pastries, contributing to the ongoing discourse surrounding their flavors and cultural significance. Future research endeavors may benefit from further refining methodologies to address these potential confounding variables.

Conclusion and Outlook

Within this paper, two studies were conducted: one comparing the sweetness of Finnish, Swedish, and German PÅgen Gifflars, and the other assessing the overall taste preference between Finnish PÅgen Gifflars and Swedish Himmelsö Buns.

The results strongly support the theory that Swedish PÅgen Gifflars are perceived as sweeter than their Finnish counterparts. Additionally, German PÅgen Gifflars are generally considered less sweet. Notably, the variations in sweetness perception persist even though the nutritional information of all PÅgen Gifflars is identical, suggesting that other factors may influence taste. Moving to the second study, the results resoundingly establish the superiority of PÅgen Gifflars over Himmelsö Fika Buns in terms of overall taste and quality.

Future studies may benefit from implementing a randomized eating order and including a broader range of participants. Additionally, avoiding the practice of cutting the buns in half can help ensure consistency in the evaluation process.

Acknowledgment

I extend my sincere thanks to all the participants for their invaluable contributions to this study. Your involvement was crucial to its success. Thank you for the great time in Åbo :)